

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-166-ADH-30% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	16	Acq. Method Set:	30%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 166
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	290.0nm
Run Time:	30.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 290.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/9/2023 21:43:28 CST		
Date Processed:	3/9/2023 22:17:40 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	21.632	564123	50.57	12855
2	25.345	551437	49.43	10872

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-245-ADH-30% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230211
Vial:	27	Acq. Method Set:	30%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 245
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	290.0nm
Run Time:	30.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 290.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	2/11/2023 16:26:31 CST		
Date Processed:	3/9/2023 22:20:52 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	22.109	217707	2.14	4787
2	25.831	9937450	97.86	204187